

A Comparative Study of English Language Skills of 8th Class Students Studying in Government and Private Secondary Schools of Bageshwar District

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Abstract

The English language is the most spoken language around the world but it is also notable that English as a language in India for more than a century. The three-language formula is applied in our schools since 1986. English is introduced as the second language in most schools, but the proficiency in the English language of the students in the government school is still very low. There are four skills of language learning listening, speaking, reading, and writing (LSRW). These four skills of teaching English should be taught from the starting of formal education and the primary or elementary stage. There are various techniques and methods to improve English language skills. The researcher argues that in the listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills of the students at the primary level who are studying in government and private schools there is a vast gap in their acquisition. The purpose of this study is to analyze the ability of class VIII students in English language learning skills in government and private schools. A sample of 150 students was taken from 9 schools in the Bageshwar district. The study employed the descriptive research method for the data collection. English Language Achievement test (ELS) for the 8th class students was prepared by the supervisor Prof. Shanti Nayal and the investigator to test the four skills of the English language among the class 8th students. The whole test was of 100 marks, it consists of four parts viz. listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills, each part contains 25 marks, and the time limit for each part was 20 minutes. The researcher adopted parametric statistics, mean, standard deviation, and 't' value statistical techniques for the study. The test was applied to measure the significant difference in the English language skills between govt. and Private schools concerning demographic variables i.e. gender, area, and type of school. The result of the study showed that there is a significant difference in English language skills between govt. and private school students.

Key words: L.S.R.W. Skills, English Language Achievement, Competency

1. Introduction

Language is our significant source of communication, it is the way through which we share our ideas, feelings, and thoughts with others. There are about 7,139 languages that are spoken in the whole world and English is the most spoken language around the world. English today has gained global status. In our country, many subjects are taught in schools. The three-language formula is applied in our schools since 1986. English is introduced as the second language in most schools, but the proficiency in the English language of the students in the government school is still very low. There are four skills of language learning listening, speaking, reading, and writing (LSRW). The first two skills may be obtained by exposure to an informal environment. But reading and writing skills have an instructional value. Therefore a sound knowledge of the principles of learning English is essential.

These four skills of teaching English should be taught from the starting of formal education and the primary or elementary stage. There are various techniques and methods to improve English language skills. The researcher argues that in the listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills of the students at the primary level who are studying in government and private schools there is a vast gap in their acquisition. The present problem was to study the ability of class VIII students in English language learning skills in government and private schools.

➤ **Need and Significance of the Study:-**

The study thoroughly deals with the concern of the English language skills among the students of class VIII studying in government and private schools. It gives a clear point about the vulnerable situation of the students toward English language skills.

➤ **Objectives of the Study**

1. To compare the English language skills of government and private school students studying in class VIII.
2. To compare the English language skills of urban and rural school students studying in class VIII.
3. To compare the English language skills of male and female school students studying in class VIII.

➤ **The Hypothesis of the Study**

Ho₁. There is no significant difference in English language skills between government and private school students studying in class VIII.

Ho₂- There is no significant difference in English language skills between male and female students studying in class VIII.

Ho₃-There is no significant difference in English language skills between rural and urban area school students studying in class VIII.

➤ **Review of the related literature:-**

(Prakash, J & Hooda, S, 2016) The study aims to study English language proficiency. A sample of 200 students studying in 10th class from government and private schools was taken. The result shows that English proficiency of private secondary schools was found better than Govt. school students. It was also found that the English proficiency of private school students was better than govt. school students in relation to area and gender. (Khaliq, B & Dwiwedi, M, 2016) The study aims to study English as a second language in govt. and private schools. For the sample, 200 students of elementary standard and 25 teachers were carried out. The study revealed that the teaching-learning situation at the primary level is far better in private schools than in government schools. (Lakhera, H. & Biswal, A., 2017) They studied strategies to enhance English language skills in students at the secondary level. For the sample, 83 students of class IX were taken for the study. A Quasi-experimental research method was used. The study revealed that teaching English language skills with the new techniques enhances the competency of the English language in the students. (Kumar, A. Ahsan, M. & Negi, M., 2017) The study aims to study the proficiency in English and the study habits of government and non-government school students. The Result showed that there is no significant difference between the study habits of students studying in government and non-government schools and also found that the English language proficiency of the students studying in non-government schools was better than the students studying in government schools.

2. Methodology

The present study employed the descriptive cum survey research method for the data collection. In the present investigation, English language learning skills (listening, **speaking, reading, and writing**) have been taken as the dependent variable, whereas demographic variables such as type of schools, gender, and locality have been taken as independent variables.

- ❖ **Area of Research:-** The study was conducted in the area of Bageshwar. For the study, Bageshwar and Kapkote blocks were taken into consideration.
- ❖ **Population:-** The students of class 8th studying in government and private schools of Bageshwar and Kapkote blocks of Bageshwar district were selected for the study.
- ❖ **Sample and Sampling Technique:-** A sample of 150 subjects were taken for the study. The sample of 150 students of class 8th located in Bageshwar district was drawn from the government and private schools of Bageshwar, in which 75 were boys students and 75 were girls students.
- ❖ **Research Tools:-** English language learning tools including listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills developed by Dr. Shanti Nayal and Ms. Kavita Tewari were used to test and assess the acquisition of English language skills among the students studying in class 8th. The whole test was of 100 marks, it

consists of four parts viz. listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills, each part contains 25 marks and a time limit of 20 minutes each. The components of the tests are as follows:-

Table 1. Components of Listening Skill Test

Components	Type of questions	Marks
Storytelling (aural)	Question/Answer	15
Literary (Audio)	True/False	10
	Total	25

Table 2. Components of Speaking Skill Test

Components	Marks
Question/answer related to their own	15
Talking about any topic	10
Total	25

Table 3 Components of Reading Skill Test

Components	Type of questions	Marks
Word with silent sound	Word pronunciation	05
Story reading	Loud reading	05
Passage reading	Very short question /answers	15
	Total	25

Table 4 Components of Writing Skill Test

Components	Type of questions	Marks
Writing on any topic	Short writing task	10
Letter writing(application)	Long writing task	15
	Total	25

- ❖ **Administration of the test:** To achieve the objectives of the present study, data were gathered by personal data schedule and English language skill achievement test. These PDS and English achievement test worksheets were distributed to the selected sample with the instruction to fill in the required data. The test was evaluated based on predefined scoring criteria, zero marks were given for wrong answers and not attempted questions.
- ❖ **Statistical techniques used:** The researcher adopted parametric statistics, mean, standard deviation, and 't' value statistical techniques for the study.

3. Results

Table 5. Comparison of English Language Skills of Government and Private School Students Studying in Class-VIII

	Government School	Private school	't' value	Level of Significance
N	75	75	16.12	Significant at 0.01
M	39.26	63.84		
S.D.	9.02	9.64		

Interpretation:

An examination of table 5 reveals that the mean, S.D. of English language skills of government and private school students is respectively 39.26, 63.84, and S.D. 9.02, 9.64. The calculated 't' value is 16.12 for the mean scores of English language skills between government and private school students studying in class VIII is significant. Thus the null hypothesis H_{01} "there is no significant difference between the scores of English language skills of

government and private school” is rejected at both levels 0.05 and 0.01. Therefore it is confirmed that the English language skills of the private school were higher than the government school students studying in class VIII. The finding agrees with the findings of **Parkash and Hooda (2016)**, who reported that the English language proficiency of private school students is more than that of government school students.

Table 6- Comparison of English Language Skills Between Male and Female School Students Studying in Class VIII

	Male Students	Female Students	't' Value	Level Of Significance
N	76	74	0.17	Non-Significant (NS)
M	52.30	52.56		
S.D.	8.95	9.04		

Interpretation:

The data presented in table 6 shows that the mean scores of the male and female students are almost similar. The mean and S.D. of the English language skills of male and female students of government and private school students studying in class VIII are 52.30, 52.56, and S.D. 8.95, 9.04 respectively. The calculation of the 't' value for the mean score is 0.17, however, it reveals that there is an insignificant difference at both levels at 0.05 and 0.01 level. H_0 - There is no significant difference in English language skills between male and female school students studying in class VIII. Both groups are similar in English language skills.

Table 7- Comparison of English Language Skills of Rural and Urban Area School Students Studying in Class VIII

	Rural students	Urban students	't' value	Level of Significance
N	68	82	4.01	Significant at 0.01
M	49.92	54.75		
S.D.	9.54	8.55		

Interpretation:-

Table 7 shows that the mean and S.D. of English language skills between rural and urban government and private school students are 49.92, 54.75 (mean) and S.D. is 9.54, 8.55 respectively. The calculated 't' value is 4.01, which is more than the standard table value at both levels of significance at 0.01 and 0.05 levels of significance. Thus the null hypothesis H_{011} - There is no significant difference in English language skills between rural and urban area school students studying in class VIII is rejected. The mean value of urban government and private students is more than the mean value of rural government and private students studying in class VIII. So it is evident that the English language skill of urban students is more than rural area students.

4. Discussion

It was observed from Table 5 that there was found a significant difference in the English language skills between the government and private school students studying in class VIII. There is found a vast difference in language skills between the government and private school students. The private school students were found higher in their English language skills than the government school students studying in class VIII. There can be many reasons for the differences among the comparative groups.

- I. The medium of instruction in government schools is Hindi which may be a reason that government school students are weak in English language skills.
- II. To learn a language practice is needed, but government school students have little chance and atmosphere to speak in the English language.

It was observed from Table 6 that there was found no significant difference in the English language skills between the male and female students studying in class VIII in government and private schools. The total male and female students were found similar in English language skills. The suitable reasons may be that both types of school students put in similar efforts in imparting English language skills education and this has a similar impact on the performance of the students.

It was observed from Table 7 that there was found a significant difference in their English language skills between the rural and urban areas school students studying in class VIII. There was found a highly significant difference in English language skills between the rural and urban areas school students. The urban students were found higher in their English language skills than the rural school's students studying in class VIII. The suitable reason for the

variance in English language skills may be that students in urban areas have a better understanding of the English language than those students living in urban areas.

5. Conclusion:

The present study was focused on the English language skills of class VIII students based on demographic variables such as type of school, gender, and locality. Based on the findings of the study and the researcher's observations during data collection it can be said that English language learning cannot be complete without learning English language skills or LSRW skills, because these skills are the complete package of learning the English language. It is established through the study that the students of government schools are comparatively weak in English language skills than the students of private schools, it shows in their set up, they have a better atmosphere for English learning, it can also be suggested that in government schools also the method of teaching of these private schools to be adopted to improve English language skills of the students. The system of government education at the elementary level is not English friendly, it cannot be denied that learning a language practice and exposure is needed and must, but in the government schools, it does not follow. The government though raised steps to improve, English language conditions in its schools, yet these steps are not sufficient to root out this very problem. English language learning should be more interesting, participative, and motivating in the classrooms. This will result in improved English language skills and communication skills.

References:

- Lakhera, H. & Biswal, A. (2017). Strategies to Enhance English Language Skills in Students at Secondary Level. *International journal of multidisciplinary approach and studies*, ISSN No::2348-537x.
- Goldberg, A. (2009). *The Nature of Generalization in Language*. America.
- Khaliq, B & Dwiwedi, M. (2016). *A comparative study of English as a second language in government and Semi- government Schools*. Retrieved from www.irjmsh.com: <https://www.academis.edu>
- Kumar, A. Ahsan, M. & Negi, M. (2017). A comparative study of proficiency in English and study habits of Government and non government school students. *International Journal of Informative and Futuristic Research*, 5, Issue-1, 8764-8770.
- Leiber, R. (1992). *Decostructing Morphology: Word Formation in Syntatic Theory*. Chicago: Chicago University Press.
- Marchand, H. (2000). *English Word Formation- a History of Research 1960-1971*. Gunter Narr.
- Martirosyan, N, Hwang, E & Wanjohi, R. (2015). *impact of English Proficiency on academic Performance of International Students*. Retrieved from <https://jistudents.org>
- Miller, J. (2000). *An Introduction to English Syntax*.
- Myerson & Rosemary, F. (1978). *Children's Knowledge of Selected Aspects of Sound Patterns of English*. Harvard University.
- Naomi, B. (1994). *Language Acquisition and Historical Change*.
- Pathak, M. (2014). *a Comparative Study of Word Formation and Sentence Formation of Class VI students Studying in Government and SEMI- Government Schools*. INdra Gandhi National OPEN University, Department of Education, New Delhi.
- Prakash, J & Hooda, S. (2016, June 28). *A comparative study of English language proficiency of students studying in government and private secondary schools of Sirsa District*. Retrieved from journalijcjr.com: <https://Journalijcjr.com>

